

Sustain Sahel

Project Title: SustainSAHEL - SYNERGISTIC USE AND PROTECTION OF NATURAL RESOURCES FOR RURAL LIVELIHOODS THROUGH SYSTEMATIC INTEGRATION OF CROPS, SHRUBS AND LIVESTOCK IN THE SAHEL

Project number: 861974

Project Acronym: SustainSAHEL

Type: Research & Innovation action

Work program topics addressed: SFS-35-2019-2020
Sustainable Intensification in Africa

Deliverable No D8.8:

Open Field Day events & associated Comms/ Diss Reports (M60)

Due date of deliverable: 31 August 2025 (M60)

Actual submission date: 31 August 2025 (M60)

Version: 1.0

Main Authors: Fernando Sousa (FiBL), Lilian Beck (UHOH)

D8.8: Open Field Day (M60)

Project ref. number	Grant Agreement No 861974
Project title	SustainSAHEL

Deliverable title	Open Field Day events & associated Comms/ Diss Reports (M60)
Deliverable number	D8.8
Deliverable version	
Contractual date of delivery	31 August 2025 (M60)
Actual date of delivery	31 August 2025 (M60)
Document status	
Document version	
Online access	
Diffusion	
Nature of deliverable	PU
Work package	WP8
Partner responsible	FiBL/CSE/UHOH
Author(s)	Fernando Sousa (FiBL), Lilian Beck (UHOH)
Editor	Carla Pinho, Harun Cicek (FiBL CH)
Approved by	Harun Cicek (FiBL CH)
REA Project Officer	Alina KOZACENKO

Keywords	Open Field days, Dissemination & Communication, learning materials, training materials
-----------------	--

Table of Contents

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
2. SUSTAINSAHEL'S DISSEMINATION STRATEGY	4
2.1 Background and relevance	4
2.2 Objectives	5
2.3 The lead farmer approach.....	6
2.4 The cascade model of dissemination.....	6
3. OPEN FIELD DAYS: A PLATFORM FOR CO-LEARNING AND TRANSDISCIPLINARY ENGAGEMENT	8
3.1 What happened on the ground	8
3.2 Reflections on farmer engagement and knowledge exchange during the open field days.....	12
3.3 Challenges in the implementation of the open field days.....	13
4. LEARNING MATERIALS.....	14
4.1 Printed learning and dissemination materials	14
4.1.1 A visual brochure that unfolds into a wall poster portraying an agroforestry system adapted to the local context:	15
4.1.2 Farmer-focused posters on scientific results	15
4.1.3 A visual brochure summarizing the key messages of WP4,5 and 7:.....	16
4.1.4 Blog posts.....	16
4.2 Videos	17
4.2.1 Distribution of mini-SD memory cards loaded with CSL related videos in the local languages:	17
4.2.2 Elaboration of new videos with Access Agriculture.....	17
4.2.2 Elaboration of additional videos based on field visits	18
4.3 New chapter on agroforestry in the Sahel in the African Organic Farming Training Manual	19
5. PARTNERSHIPS WITHIN AND BEYOND SUSTAINSAHEL	19
5.1 Interactions with other work packages.....	19
5.2 Expanding the project's outreach.....	20
5.2.1 Collaboration with the DAAPS project	20
5.2.2 Collaboration with other H2020 and EU-DESIRA projects.....	21
4. APPENDIX – IMAGES OF SUSTAINSAHEL'S OPEN FIELD DAYS	23

1. Executive summary

SustainSahel's dissemination strategy, implemented between 2022 and 2025, was built around a progressive cascade approach that combined centralized training with decentralized, farmer-led outreach. At the heart of this strategy were the open field days, which served not only as dissemination events but also as key platforms for transdisciplinary collaboration and co-learning among farmers, researchers, students, and extension officers. A total of 123 open field day events have been organized between 2022 and 2025, with a total of 4,893 participations—2,177 in Mali, 1,683 in Senegal, and 1,033 in Burkina Faso. The two-phase dissemination approach began with the training of lead farmers, who were gradually empowered to become facilitators themselves during the second, decentralized phase. This transition has amplified peer-to-peer learning and allowed project messages and practices to spread organically across new villages and farming communities. Alongside the events, the project prioritized the development of accessible, context-specific learning materials, co-designed with farmers and tailored to local realities. Most of these materials were integrated into the open field day activities. These consisted of brochures, videos and posters. For example, seven farmer-focused posters—covering topics such as mulching with native bushes, alley cropping, and the use of shrub cuttings as fodder—were produced and distributed. These materials not only supported farmer learning but also provided a valuable exercise in transdisciplinary communication, encouraging researchers to translate their findings into formats accessible to end users. The open field days are embedded within a broader systemic dissemination approach that includes connections to Innovation Platforms and a project knowledge-sharing forum. This deliverable offers an overview of the outcomes and evolution of SustainSahel's dissemination strategy, highlighting its achievements, which point to a successful implementation that had as a focus the deepening of local ownership and long-term impact.

2. SustainSahel's Dissemination Strategy

2.1 Background and relevance

The dissemination strategy of the SustainSahel project was collaboratively developed by all project partners at the end of 2021. This joint drafting process marked a pivotal moment in reorienting the activities of Work Package 8 (WP8), following the unexpected yet necessary change in leadership earlier that year.

In 2021, project partner MINERVA (UK) was formally removed from the consortium by mutual agreement. This decision stemmed from challenges related to limited understanding of the local context and working culture, as well as a mismatch between the expertise required and that available for leading WP8. To address the gap, FiBL assumed leadership of WP8, leveraging its strong experience in West Africa and capacity to coordinate dissemination activities effectively.

The resulting dissemination strategy outlined a comprehensive action plan, including key milestones and a distribution of responsibilities among partners. One of the strategy's defining strengths was its early implementation in the project timeline, which contrasts with the more usual approach in research for development projects, where dissemination occurs mainly at the end of the project. This early start enabled the gradual building of trust among project partners, farmers, and other stakeholders, which proved essential for meaningful engagement and long-term collaboration. It also provided a robust foundation for the co-creation of agendas, content, and learning materials for subsequent dissemination events, particularly the open field days.

D8.8: Open Field Day (M60)

The strategy served as a practical framework for local teams, guiding the organization of open field days and helping harmonize approaches across the three implementation countries. This harmonization focused on:

1. Using a shared agenda structure for field day events;
2. Ensuring a consistent number of events per project site;
3. Coordinating follow-up activities with lead farmers using similar methods.

Despite this harmonized structure, the open field day events were tailored to reflect the rich cultural and ecological diversity of each location, as well as the unique composition and dynamics of local teams and the co-selected innovations under trial.

In alignment with the local dissemination strategy, teams were advised to organize two open field days per year in the first phase of the dissemination strategy (2022 and 2023). The first event, scheduled before the onset of the rainy season, aimed to introduce farmers to the key concepts and practices related to the tested innovations. The second event, held toward the end of the season, provided an opportunity to assess the visible effects of the different treatments and foster discussion around outcomes, challenges, and next steps. The different phases of the dissemination strategy are explained in detail in section 2.4 below.

The open field days worked in complementarity with the innovation platforms (IP), in which some of the lead farmers also participated, providing a platform to deepen the discussions of the content of the open field days and the practices that were demonstrated.

2.2 Objectives

The dissemination strategy is embedded in the overarching objectives of the project, which seeks to enhance the resilience of farming systems in the Sahel through the study and dissemination of appropriate crop-shrub/tree-livestock (CSL) management practices. The main goals of this strategy can be summarized as follows:

1. To disseminate appropriate CSL management practices in six of the project sites: Ouarkhokh, Niakhar (Senegal); Koulikoro, Sikasso (Mali); Saria, Yilou (Burkina Faso);
2. To integrate relevant existing knowledge with new one emanating from the project's results, in a spirit of transdisciplinary collaboration between all project partners;
3. To work closely with other work packages in order to maximize the synergies between different activities, such as the study of the socio-economic impact of the disseminated practices (particularly with WP3); the innovation platforms' discussions (coordinated by WP2), which can greatly benefit from the inputs and interlinkages with the dissemination process; and the new project mechanism, SustainSahel's internal sharing forum (jointly coordinated by WP8 and WP2);
4. To empower smallholder farmers to become the owners and disseminators of the practices themselves, in all of the project sites. This applies firstly to the lead farmers, who are directly engaged with the project in a continuous way between 2022 and 2025, but also to other farmers in their villages.

2.3 The lead farmer approach

This approach lies at the core of the project's dissemination strategy and was considered by all partners as an innovative way of disseminating results. In each site, a group of lead farmers was formed, each of them representing one village. In the case of Burkina Faso, the local partners chose two farmers per village. The lead farmers remained the same group of farmers that followed the project dissemination strategy between 2022 and 2025, except in the case of the site of Niakhar, where the initial selection of lead farmers was changed in 2023 due to the lack of availability of those selected (due to off-farm jobs, mostly in education) – this is explained in more detail in the section 3.3, below.

2.4 The cascade model of dissemination

In its initial phase, the SustainSahel dissemination approach focused on centralized open field days, where lead farmers—along with, in some cases, innovation platform (IP) members, extension officers, and other local actors—were invited to a single demonstration site per region. These events proved highly effective for logistical coordination and for providing a unified introduction to the set of agroecological practices being promoted. However, it became clear that continuing this same format throughout the project risked diminishing engagement due to repetition and lack of local contextualization.

As a result, the local dissemination action plans were structured into **two distinct phases**, each designed to build on the other and gradually increase local ownership and outreach capacity.

Phase 1 – Training and Empowerment of Lead Farmers (2022–2023)

During this phase, lead farmers, project members, and other stakeholders gathered at demonstration sites to exchange research findings and field experiences. Through participation in open field days, lead farmers were introduced to a variety of innovations and encouraged to test selected practices in their own fields, based on personal interest and local relevance.

This phase was conceptualized as a capacity-building stage, equipping lead farmers to become future trainers within their communities. To support this, each lead farmer received a minimum of two field visits from local extension officers during the rainy season. These visits aimed to provide ongoing guidance, address technical challenges, and ensure correct implementation of the practices.

Importantly, this process took place alongside the Innovation Platform activities, creating opportunities for mutual learning and feedback between farmer-led experimentation and broader innovation processes.

Phase 2 – Decentralized Dissemination through Farmer-Led Events (2024–2025)

By the end of Phase 1, lead farmers had typically participated in at least two—and in some cases up to four or five—open field days, and had been visited approximately four times by extension officers. With this accumulated knowledge and hands-on experience, they are now well-positioned to assume a more active role in dissemination.

Starting in the 2024 rainy season, these lead farmers are expected to host small-scale open field days in their own fields. These localized events will target neighboring farmers and be supported by local extension officers. This decentralized approach will amplify the cascading effect of the project's dissemination strategy, allowing innovations to reach new villages and farming communities beyond the original project sites.

D8.8: Open Field Day (M60)

This strategic shift from centralized to farmer-led, site-specific dissemination represents a key evolution in the SustainSahel project’s outreach methodology—moving from demonstration to implementation, and from top-down transfer to peer-to-peer learning.

Figure 1 and 2. The shift of the project’s dissemination approach from a centralized open field day approach to a decentralized one, with lead farmers becoming trainers of other farmers.

3. Open Field Days: A platform for co-learning and transdisciplinary engagement

3.1 What happened on the ground

Over the course of three years, the open field day events have proven to be enriching experiences for both lead farmers and project partners, reinforcing the project's transdisciplinary and co-learning approach. These events offered a dynamic platform where farmers, researchers, and students engaged in meaningful exchanges—through shared presentations, field visits, and live demonstrations of sustainable practices.

The field days typically featured a combination of theoretical inputs and practical sessions. PhD students and researchers working with SustainSahel presented their findings and experiences from the demonstration plots, while expert and farmer-led demonstrations illustrated CSL techniques such as the proper method of cutting native bushes such as *Guiera* and *Piliostigma* and using the biomass as mulch. These presentations were followed by group visits to the fields, where all participants collectively assessed the visible effects of different treatments on crop performance.

Beyond the technical content, the social setting of the field days—often culminating in a shared meal—provided an informal space for dialogue, reflection, and feedback. Farmers regularly took the opportunity to voice their opinions, pose questions, and debate the relevance and outcomes of the practices demonstrated. This environment facilitated mutual understanding and learning, where scientific knowledge and local experience could meet and evolve together.

The lead farmers who participated in the two phases of the project's dissemination approach were distributed as follows:

- Senegal: 39 lead farmers in Niakhar and 30 lead farmers in Ouarkhokh
- Mali: 40 lead farmers in Koulikoro and 40 lead farmers in Sikasso
- Burkina Faso: 40 lead farmers in Saria and 40 lead farmers in Yilou

While in Senegal and Mali, each lead farmer represented one village, in Burkina Faso, two farmers were selected per village. In the case of Senegal, one farmer dropped out from the group in Niakhar in 2023 and was not replaced. In Ouarkhokh, the number of lead farmers is lower because this is a sparsely populated area.

In total, 123 dissemination events in both phases have been organized in the 6 sites of the three countries between 2022 and 2025: 59 in Mali, 17 in Burkina Faso and 47 in Senegal. The differences in the numbers of the events are related to the specific strategies of the local teams. For example, in Burkina Faso, instead of opting for one smaller event per village like in Mali or Niakhar, the team organized four smaller events in selected villages and invited lead farmers from the others to join. In Senegal, the decentralized events of phase 2 were only organized in Niakhar. It was a strategic choice for the Senegalese team to focus their dissemination resources in Niakhar due to the relevance it has for the work of evaluation of innovation adoption performed by WP3 but also because Ouarkhokh is significantly farther. The bulk of the events happened between 2022 and 2024, with only three events in 2025, all in Mali. A total of 4893 participations was recorded for all the events, 2177 for Mali, 1033 for Burkina Faso, and 1683 for Senegal. The higher number of participations in Mali is because the events were always attended by other farmers from the villages where the events took place. In Senegal, this was also the case for the phase 2 events in Niakhar.

D8.8: Open Field Day (M60)

A summary of all of the dissemination events, including dates, number of participants, location and the type of event can be seen in table I below.

Table I. Dates and attendance of the 123 open field day events organized between 2022 and 2025 in the six project sites.

Country	Site	Phase	Date	Participants*	Location	Short description
Mali	Koulikoro	1	11/06/2022	77	Mafeya	Open field day at village level for all lead farmers and other local farmers
			24/10/2022	97	Tiètikila	Open field day at village level for all lead farmers and other local farmers
			19/10/2022	167	IPR research station	Open field day at research station for all lead farmers and other local farmers
			29/05/2023	74	IPR research station	Open field day at village level for all lead farmers and other local farmers Open field day at research station for all lead farmers and other local farmers
			30/10/2023	98	Banani	Open field day at village level for all lead farmers and other local farmers
			11/11/2023	70	IPR research station	Open field day at research station for all lead farmers and other local farmers
			04/05/2024	54	IPR research station	Open field day at research station for all lead farmers and other local farmers
			28/05/2024	36	Koulikoro	Special dissemination session only for lead farmers
			2	12/07/2024	10	Kalankoulou
		13/07/2024	4	Ngolobougou	Open field day at village level	
		14/07/2024	4	Karadiè	Open field day at village level	
		15/07/2024	10	Est	Open field day at village level	
		16/07/2024	5	Ngabakoro	Open field day at village level	
		17/07/2024	10	Koyo	Open field day at village level	
		18/07/2024	5	Hamaribougou	Open field day at village level	
		19/07/2024	5	Doribougou	Open field day at village level	
		20/07/2024	10	Dièni	Open field day at village level	
		21/07/2024	4	Bambara	Open field day at village level	
		22/07/2024	5	Kabana	Open field day at village level	
		23/07/2024	10	Wolonkotoba sokoura	Open field day at village level	
		24/07/2024	7	Wolonkotoba sokoro	Open field day at village level	
		25/07/2024	6	Fassa	Open field day at village level	
		26/07/2024	10	Bougounissaba	Open field day at village level	
		26/07/2024	10	Niamakorobougou	Open field day at village level	
		27/07/2024	4	Massala	Open field day at village level	

D8.8: Open Field Day (M60)

			28/07/2024	5	Fougadougou	Open field day at village level
			29/07/2024	2	Manabougou	Open field day at village level
			30/07/2024	6	Foura	Open field day at village level
			31/07/2024	4	Daforo	Open field day at village level
			01/08/2024	6	Diogo	Open field day at village level
			02/08/2024	5	Semba-est	Open field day at village level
			03/08/2024	5	Semba-ouest	Open field day at village level
			04/08/2024	5	Gombala	Open field day at village level
			05/08/2024	5	Dogoni	Open field day at village level
			06/08/2024	4	Tanabougou	Open field day at village level
			07/08/2024	5	Mafeya	Open field day at village level
			08/08/2024	5	Sho	Open field day at village level
			09/08/2024	5	Dladiè	Open field day at village level
			15/11/2024	9	Koulikoro	Open field day at village level
			11/07/2025	98	Koulikoro.	Special dissemination session for lead farmers and other local farmers on project results
			18/07/2025	68	Koulikoro.	Special dissemination session for lead farmers and other local farmers on project results
	Sikasso	1	04/06/2022	74	Zoumana Djassa	Open field day at village level for all lead farmers and other local farmers
			31/10/2022	72	Zoumana Djassa	Open field day at village level for all lead farmers and other local farmers
			02/06/2023	96	IER Research station	Open field day at research station for all lead farmers and other local farmers
			07/11/2023	97	Sikasso	Open field day at village level for all lead farmers and other local farmers
			29/05/2024	35	Klela	Special dissemination session only for lead farmers
		2	15/07/2024	54	Gonkasso	Open field day at village level
			16/07/2024	50	Korobedougou	Open field day at village level
			17/07/2024	48	Dougoumousso	Open field day at village level
			18/07/2024	74	Natoumana	Open field day at village level
			19/07/2024	51	Klela	Open field day at village level
			20/07/2024	51	Kouroumasso	Open field day at village level
			14/08/2024	83	Natoumana	Open field day at village level
			15/08/2024	39	Gonkasso	Open field day at village level
			18/08/2024	46	Dougoumousso	Open field day at village level
			19/08/2024	62	Klela	Open field day at village level
			20/08/2024	57	Kouroumasso	Open field day at village level
			23/08/2024	60	Korobedougou	Open field day at village level
			16/07/2025	99	IER Research station	Open field day at research station for all lead farmers and other local farmers
Burkina Faso	Saria	1	31/05/2022	70	Saria	Open field day at research station with field visits to nearby farmers' fields

D8.8: Open Field Day (M60)

			26/09/2022	90	Saria	Open field day at research station with field visits to nearby farmers' fields	
			12/05/2023	62	Saria	Open field day at research station with field visits to nearby farmers' fields	
			27/10/2023	53	Saria	Open field day at research station with field visits to nearby farmers' fields	
		2	28/10/2024	57	Itaoré	Open field day at village level	
		01/11/2024	51	Tibrele	Open field day at village level		
		29/10/2024	57	Doulou	Open field day at village level		
		30/10/2024	54	Nanjala	Open field day at village level		
		31/10/2024	48	Tamplega	Open field day at village level		
		Yilou	1	30/05/2022	70	Yilou	Open field day at research station with field visits to nearby farmers' fields
				03/11/2022	80	Yilou	Open field day at research station with field visits to nearby farmers' fields
	09/05/2023			65	Yilou	Open field day at research station with field visits to nearby farmers' fields	
	24/10/2023			53	Yilou	Open field day at research station with field visits to nearby farmers' fields	
	2		06/11/2024	53	Gougré	Open field day at village level	
	04/11/2024		57	Guibaré	Open field day at village level		
	04/11/2024		54	Yilou	Open field day at village level		
	08/11/2024		59	Sindri	Open field day at village level		
	Senegal	Niakhar	1	21/06/2022	24	Sanghai	Open field day at village level for all lead farmers and other local farmers
				23/09/2022	29	Diohine	Open field day at village level for all lead farmers and other local farmers
				27/04/2023	65	Niakhar	Open field day at village level for all lead farmers and other local farmers
				03/11/2023	51	Sanghai	Open field day at village level for all lead farmers and other local farmers
2			05/05/2024 to 16/05/2024	1348	39 different villages**	Open field day at 39 different villages** in the region of Niakhar	
Ouarkhokh			1	23/06/2022	35	Oaukhokh	Open field day at village level for all lead farmers and other local farmers
				21/09/2022	38	Oaukhokh	Open field day at village level for all lead farmers and other local farmers
		25/04/2023		48	Oaukhokh	Open field day at village level for all lead farmers and other local farmers	

D8.8: Open Field Day (M60)

			30/10/2023	45	Oaukhokh	Open field day at village level for all lead farmers and other local farmers
--	--	--	------------	----	----------	--

*The number of total participants includes lead farmers and other stakeholder, such as Innovation platform’s members, other farmers from the village, representatives of the farmers’ organization, research institution and extension structures.

**The villages where events were organized in the Niakhar site in phase 2 were: Ndoundokh, Diohine, Pédjiré, Kothiokh, Mokane, Ngouye, Mbokane, Diarékh, Ndouf, Doudame, Ndongolor, Tokasso, N dofane, Boure, Languéme, Godaguéne, Sanghaie, Sagne, Yénguélé, Sass Mack, Sob, Mboyenne, Boof Coop, Diaoulé, Diamcira, Boof Ndémbéne, Ndiop, Mbélbouck, Thiaré, Nguékhokh, Thiouthioune, Tiaré, Kouléme Hameau, Toucar, Keur Bouca, Sakhao Peul, Mbéllacadio, Poulock, Ndiosmone, Bacobof, Keur Mangarie, Toucar, Poudaye, Ndiambour sine, Diandoum, and Diané.

3.2 Reflections on farmer engagement and knowledge exchange during the open field days

The open field days served as a cornerstone for fostering collaboration among project partners, offering a concrete opportunity for joint planning and execution. These events became a catalyst for the project’s transdisciplinary approach, enabling diverse stakeholders—including farmers’ organizations, researchers from multiple disciplines, and members of innovation platforms (many of whom are farmers themselves)—to co-develop the agenda and define how the CSL practices should be disseminated.

This collaborative process marked the practical launch of the project’s co-creation model. It facilitated mutual learning and knowledge exchange, encouraging farmers and other stakeholders to collectively identify key messages and co-design communication formats. However, the process also highlighted some initial challenges. Local teams often faced obstacles such as language barriers and entrenched stereotypes, which reflected and reinforced the traditionally fragmented relationships between disciplines, and between academic and non-academic actors.

Over time, and through repeated interaction, these barriers began to erode. One of the most significant outcomes—clearly articulated during the project’s annual meeting in February 2023 in Burkina Faso—was the emergence of genuine collaboration and a gradual dissolution of rigid boundaries between different participant groups. The co-organization of open field days not only enhanced the effectiveness of dissemination but also strengthened the foundation for inclusive, transdisciplinary partnerships central to the SustainSahel approach.

One of the interesting findings from the field days is the diversity in farmers’ existing knowledge and familiarity with CSL and agroecological practices across the different project sites. For example, farmers in **Yilou** demonstrated comparatively higher levels of awareness and experience with techniques such as mulching, assisted natural regeneration, living fences, and other agroforestry practices. In contrast, participants in **Niakhar** and **Ouarkhokh** were often encountering certain concepts—such as the use of mulch from native bush cuttings—for the first time, and many expressed surprise and curiosity about these approaches.

Similarly, farmers in **Koulikoro** and **Sikasso** noted their surprise upon learning that their peers in Burkina Faso did not burn spontaneous native bushes prior to the rainy season, but instead used them as mulch to enhance soil fertility and moisture retention. These cross-site discoveries sparked lively discussions and highlighted the potential of farmer-to-farmer learning within the project’s broader dissemination efforts.

D8.8: Open Field Day (M60)

The reasons for these differences in baseline knowledge are not yet fully understood but are likely influenced by a complex mix of ecological, cultural, historical, and institutional factors. As such, the project will continue to explore these differences in the remaining phases of research and experience-sharing.

Understanding the varying levels of knowledge across sites proved critical for tailoring the content and structure of the open field days. For instance, techniques that were novel and eye-opening for farmers in Niakhar may not have held the same value for more experienced farmers in Yilou. In these latter cases, deeper technical discussions—such as the interactions between livestock and shrub cover currently explored in Work Package 6—offered more relevant and stimulating learning opportunities.

These insights informed the planning of subsequent open field days, which adopted more site-specific agendas. This adaptive approach not only respected local realities and knowledge systems but also maximized engagement, relevance, and the potential for meaningful knowledge uptake.

The open field days in summary:

- **Field days combined theory with practice**, featuring presentations by researchers and PhD students alongside expert and farmer-led demonstrations of CSL techniques such as cutting native bushes (e.g. Guiera, Piliostigma) and using biomass as mulch, alley farming with the legume tree *Leucaena*, or composting with the cuttings of native trees and bushes.
- **A total of 123 open field day events were organized** between 2022 and 2025 across six sites in three countries, engaging 4,893 participations, with variation in strategies and reach reflecting local contexts and team priorities.
- **The decentralized phase strengthened local ownership**, with lead farmers becoming disseminators of CSL practices themselves and demonstrating a functional cascade model as well as enabling broader peer-to-peer learning.
- **Open field days fostered co-learning** between farmers, researchers, and students through presentations, field visits, and practical demonstrations, reinforcing the project's transdisciplinary goals.
- **Informal exchanges** during shared meals enabled farmers to provide feedback, ask questions, and engage in open dialogue, enhancing trust and mutual understanding.
- **Knowledge levels varied significantly across sites**: for example, farmers in Yilou were more familiar with agroecological practices like mulching and living fences than those in Niakhar or Ouarkhokh.
- **Cross-site learning revealed surprises and inspiration**, such as Malian farmers discovering non-burning mulching practices in Burkina Faso, sparking interest in new approaches.

3.3 Challenges in the implementation of the open field days

The implementation of the local dissemination action plan faced some challenges. Despite that, the local teams managed to organize most of the proposed open field day events between 2022 and 2025, showing great commitment and dedication to the purpose of these activities. The three main challenges faced by the local teams can be summarized as follows:

- The accessibility of some parts of the intervention areas was at times very challenging, especially during the rainy season. Some villages in the target regions become inaccessible after heavy rains, making it difficult to access them or for the lead farmers in remote areas to come to the open

D8.8: Open Field Day (M60)

field day events. In case of getting stuck in mud, vehicles can face many hours of waiting before being towed away by the nearest help available. In some events, extension officers visited the villages by motorbike. Despite that, even motorbikes could not reach some villages after particularly heavy rain spells.

- During the last 5 years, some Sahelian countries have seen a surge in insecurity due to rebel militias controlling parts of, for example, Mali and Burkina Faso. The neighboring regions of Koulikoro, Sikasso, and Yilou sites deserve special attention, making up half of the project's sites. This was determined, for example, by relocating the organization of the dissemination event of 07/11/2023 in the Sikasso site to the town of Sikasso, instead of the village of Zoumana Diassa. Meanwhile, the security situation improved dramatically since 2024, which made it easier to continue with the implementation of the dissemination strategy.
- The implementation of the local open field day events in Niakhar, Senegal, faced some challenges in the mobilization of the lead farmers in 2022. One of the issues was that the lead farmers were solely appointed by the village traditional leaders, who selected generally the most educated villagers, many of them school teachers. Because the school calendar was not compatible with the open field day events' agenda, the mobilization of the initially selected lead farmers was very poor. A new mission with different project members took place in January 2023 to co-select other lead farmers in the site of Niakhar, in collaboration with the traditional leaders, where the project's objectives were made clearer. The following dissemination event in Niakhar (27th April 2023) counted with a much higher attendance, thanks to this adjustment. The remaining dissemination events since then, in November 2023 and in May 2024, have counted as well with a high attendance rate.

4. Learning materials

An essential element of SustainSahel's dissemination strategy is the development of context-appropriate learning materials concerning CSL practices, co-designed and refined iteratively with farmers. Given the challenges in the project areas, including widespread illiteracy, limited access to information, gender and generational disparities, and weak or absent extension services, the project is piloting innovative learning tools to improve farmers' access to practical knowledge on CSL practices.

Most of the learning materials described below have been shared with lead farmers during open field days or other special dissemination events.

4.1 Printed learning and dissemination materials

These posters and brochures **are designed to facilitate exchange and convey co-developed agroforestry practices and key lessons**, making them usable both during project events and beyond, for wider dissemination. Consequently, the strategy focuses on producing tailored knowledge products to support extension actors in maintaining and disseminating project knowledge beyond the project's lifespan. Thereby, the knowledge products are developed integrating feedback loops from farmers and collaborating scientists: For instance, the posters were presented in Innovation Platform meetings in Burkina Faso and Senegal and discussed with the farmers, scientists, and extension actors. This provided a feedback loop allowing for the integration of local knowledge, scientific expertise, and farmers' expertise, and improved the way to communicate research insights to the targeted audience. The posters are

available now for download and integrated in the Organic Manual chapters, which provide in-depth background knowledge and didactical suggestions. This way it can be used as a guide to organize workshops with farmers and facilitate learning on agroforestry in the Sahel, supported by the posters and brochures.

4.1.1 A visual brochure that unfolds into a wall poster portraying an agroforestry system adapted to the local context:

A visual brochure showing the benefits of trees and shrubs for the local agricultural systems was produced in 2023. A total of 500 copies were printed and distributed to lead farmers in the three countries. The brochure has little text and relies on pictures and illustrations to convey the main messages. It also includes a list of relevant species to be included in the fields and the respective benefits. The illustrated example of a suitable agroforestry system for the Sahel was collaboratively designed by the production team and the project's experts. This first version will be a test version to be assessed by lead farmers. The two-fold use of this learning material, as a brochure or a wall poster, makes its use by farmers more flexible, since they can read the brochure and pass it on to others, and/or use it as a wall poster, something that is quite appreciated by local farmers. All the illustrations in the brochure were made by a professional illustrator based in East Africa, specifically for SustainSahel. The brochure is also available on [Zenodo](#).

4.1.2 Farmer-focused posters on scientific results

Under the guidance of FiBL and CSE, local research teams in Senegal, Mali, and Burkina Faso developed farmer-focused posters illustrating key practices tested and disseminated by the project – in an innovative way to disseminate scientific results in a visual way. Designed to be accessible and visually engaging, these posters depict the integration of trees, shrubs, crops, and livestock.

The process of creating the posters required researchers to step into the shoes of farmers—adapting their language and presentation style to the needs of non-academic audiences. This proved to be a valuable transdisciplinary exercise, strengthening researchers' communication skills while making research findings more directly accessible to farmers.

In 2024, four posters were produced with active input from scientists involved in WP4 and WP5. Each was printed in A4 format for distribution to lead farmers, alongside larger A3 versions to be displayed publicly in villages, facilitating peer learning. Topics included mulch application with native bush species, alley cropping, biomass use to enhance yields, and woody fodder conservation.

Titles of the posters with WP4 and WP5 results:

- Improved formulations for mulching on site
- Farmer mulching of shrub biomass in sorghum plots
- Mulching with millet residues
- Mulching with *Guiera Senegalensis*

Another set of posters were produced in collaboration with research teams from WP6 and WP7 in 2025, to disseminate their research. These posters were shared and discussed with farmers on Innovation platform meetings in Burkina Faso and Senegal.

D8.8: Open Field Day (M60)

Titles of the posters:

- Application of medicinal trees and shrubs to treat gastrointestinal nematode infestations
- Improving yields by integrating a diversity of shrubs or trees into crop fields
- *Faidherbia* boosting yields through creating fertility islands
- Organic matter matters: Different methods to add organic matter and their influence on yields and soil health
- Cut and drop mulching practices with local shrubs to encourage soil productivity

The posters are publicly available and can be downloaded from the [project's website](#).

4.1.3 A visual brochure summarizing the key messages of WP4,5 and 7:

A brochure that distills the key findings from Work Packages 4, 5, and 6, using engaging visuals, field photography and infographics to bring the data to life. It is tailored to diverse stakeholder groups—policy makers, scientists, advisors, and farmers—ensuring each sees relevant insights clearly highlighted. Policy makers will gain immediate clarity on actionable evidence, scientists will appreciate distilled, data-driven takeaways for further research, extension actors and farmers can quickly grasp practical implications. The result is a user-friendly communication tool: visually rich, entirely evidence-based, and designed to bridge research and real-world impact.

This brochure will be uploaded soon to the project's website.

4.1.4 Blog posts

To reach a broader audience, three blog posts were written and published on the GIZ facilitated “Knowledge Platform on organic agriculture and agroecology in africa” in English and French. These blog posts also serve as a resource library for extension actors, providing content on topics relevant to their field. The blog posts feature videos and extension materials created through the project, offering practical resources for extension actors and other stakeholders.

<https://kcoa-africa.org/fr/decouvrir-les-secrets-de-larbre-miracle-faidherbia-albida/>

<https://kcoa-africa.org/fr/du-sable-a-labondance-verte-2/>

<https://kcoa-africa.org/uncovering-secrets-of-the-miracle-tree-faidherbia-albida/>

4.1.5. Children's book

A children's book was written by WP8 collaborator Lilian Beck and illustrated by West-African illustrator Deogratius G Okudi with the idea that sharing tree regeneration and protection messages with children is crucial—it builds empathy, informs young minds about the importance of trees for animals, and encourages practical actions that spread into families and communities. The assumption is that children may internalize these ideas early on and carry them as values into adulthood. It further promotes ecological literacy and systems thinking, and could, for example, be integrated in local schools.

D8.8: Open Field Day (M60)

The children's book explains in an empathic way the importance of trees and shrubs for life and “the interwovenness of the miraculous world of soil organisms, trees, climate, animals, and food”. But also how one can boost thriving tree growth through simple and concrete actions by sharing agroforestry best practices identified by the Sustain Sahel project.

4.1.6. Best practice calendar on local shrubs for animal well-being

WP8 in cooperation with WP6 is developing a seasonal calendar showcasing recommended seasonal activities for forage harvesting of local trees and shrubs, application of local shrubs and trees for medical purposes, and local tree and shrub propagation practices as well as natural assisted regeneration practices—helping integrate livestock systems with local woody plant species throughout the year.

This is a visual **seasonal calendar**—using icons, simple illustrations, photography, and colour-coded panels—designed to function without text. It makes knowledge accessible across the three partner countries (and beyond), allowing farmers of different languages and literacy levels to apply seasonal practices on their own farms. Further information can be found in the deliverable D6.6.

4.2 Videos

4.2.1 Distribution of mini-SD memory cards loaded with CSL related videos in the local languages:

All lead farmers received a mini-SD memory card with nine videos portraying CSL related videos translated into the local languages of each site. The decision to use the video on mobile-phone approach is related to the fact that all lead farmers either have a mobile phone compatible with the use of mini-SD memory cards or have at least one family member who has it. Farmers in the intervention areas have the habit of watching videos on their mobile phones for entertainment or learning, which makes this learning tool well adapted to the local context. The nine videos were collaboratively selected with Access Agriculture from their large online video database, considering their relevance regarding the use of CSL practices. The videos had to be dubbed into the local languages of the six project sites, in case those versions didn't exist already. The mini-SD cards were shared with farmers in the second open field day events of 2022, and by the beginning of 2023 in case of Sikasso.

4.2.2 Elaboration of new videos with Access Agriculture

Videos are an important component of SustainSahel's dissemination strategy because they are well adapted to the target audience of the project. Videos can easily convey relevant information in a visual and engaging way. Furthermore, the need for new videos on agroforestry practices is clear, since they were almost inexistent on Access Agriculture video database up until the project's contributions. The table below shows the new videos produced by Access Agriculture in the framework of SustainSahel.

Table 2. Videos produced by Access Agriculture

Video	Countries	Languages	Status
Use of West African indigenous bush biomass for mulch (Guiera senegalensis, Piliostigma reticulatum)	Burkina Faso	English, Bambara, Pulaar, Mooré, French, Wolof, Serere,	Finalized and online [Link]
Managing intestinal nematodes in small ruminants	Burkina Faso	English, Bambara, Pulaar, Mooré, French, Wolof, Serere,	Finalized and online [link]
Alley cropping with Gliricidia sepium and Leucaena leucocephala	Mali	English, Bambara, Pulaar, Mooré, French, Wolof, Serere,	Finalized and will be uploaded by end of August 2025
Propagation of legume trees appropriate for agroforestry systems in the Sahel	Mali, Burkina Faso	English, Bambara, Pulaar, Mooré, French, Wolof, Serere,	Finalized and online [Link]

4.2.2 Elaboration of additional videos based on field visits

Initially hired by the project as an intern and later as a collaborator in WP8 team through the University of Hohenheim, the agroforestry specialist Lilian Beck has expanded the wealth of project videos with material from her field trips in the scope of the project, as can be seen in the table below. These videos were not expected in the initial DoA.

Table 3. Videos produced by Lilian Beck

Video	Languages	Status
Un exemple de ferme agroforestière au Sahel	French, Bambara, Serere, Mooré, English, Wolof, Pulaar,	Finalized and online [Link]
Avantages de l'agroforesterie au Sahel	French, Bambara, Serere, Mooré, English, Wolof, Pulaar,	Finalized and online [link]
Uncovering secrets of the Miracle Tree Faidherbia albida	French, English	Finalized and online [Link]
Shrub and tree propagation in an on-farm nursery	French, Wolof	Finalized and online [Link]
Composting local shrubs for improving soil and yields (Guiera)	French, Wolof	Finalized
Natural Assisted Regeneration of local shrubs and trees	French, Wolof	In postproduction phase
Growing trees in sandy soil	French, Wolof	Finalized

Faidherbia propagation	French, Wolof	In post-production phase
Best practice combination : Mulching, irrigation, and composting	French	In post-production phase
Short: Rainwater harvesting practices in the Sahel	French, English	In post-production phase

4.3 New chapter on agroforestry in the Sahel in the African Organic Farming Training Manual

SustainSahel's WP8 team is working on a new chapter of FiBL's African Organic Farming Training Manual, focused on agroforestry and with study cases from the Sahel. Once completed, the chapter will be made [available online](#).

The chapter consists of the following four subsections:

1. **Beneficial Agroforestry Practices in the Sahel**
This subsection will present key agroforestry practices that improve soil health, water retention, and crop productivity in the Sahel, with a focus on techniques such as integrating and mulching of indigenous trees and shrubs.
2. **Improving Livestock Wellbeing Using Local Trees and Shrubs in the Sahel**
This part will explore how indigenous trees and shrubs support livestock by providing shade, fodder, and nutritional supplements.
3. **Assisted Natural Regeneration of Trees and Shrubs**
This subsection will describe methods to promote the natural regrowth of woody vegetation, enhancing biodiversity and land resilience.
4. **Propagation of Trees and Shrubs in the Sahel**
This section will offer practical guidance on the propagation of native tree and shrub species adapted to Sahelian conditions, including nursery and direct seeding techniques.

The chapter builds on scientific insights from the project and incorporates created illustrations to explain key concepts, such as ecosystem services. It also includes videos and educational materials like posters developed for the project, tailored for use by extension actors. Aimed at being a practical and accessible resource, the chapter is designed to support participatory and engaging workshops with farmers. To this end, each subsection provides didactical suggestions to guide effective field application.

5. Partnerships within and beyond SustainSahel

5.1 Interactions with other work packages

The sharing forum: Synthesizing the key project recommendations (WP8/WP2)

A project Sharing Forum was created by WP2 and WP8 in order to gather and assess the key messages of the project, while facilitating the flow of information between partners and across work packages.

D8.8: Open Field Day (M60)

During the annual meeting in February 2024, in Bamako, the messages compiled by the Sharing Forum were analysed in group sessions, which proved to be a very insightful and useful exercise for partners to gain an overview of the key findings of the project so far.

Since then, members of all work packages have met online several times during 2024 and 2025 to continue the fine-tuning of the list of messages based on the ongoing research and continuously updating it with the latest results. In the final project meeting in May 2025, the project team worked on this list of messages in three parallel workshops that resulted in three different documents targeting the main target audiences of the project:

- Recommendations for farmers and extension officers
- Recommendations for researchers
- Recommendations for policy makers

The first two sets of recommendations were presented to the general public in the [Agroforestry symposium](#) organized by SustainSahel in Dakar on the 15th of May 2025. The third set of recommendations was presented in a special policy event organized on the following day, targeting policy makers in Senegal. These three sets of recommendations will be polished and made public in the project's website.

SustainSahel impact evaluation (WP3)

WP3 carried out an impact evaluation based on randomized control treatments (RCT) approaches in order to assess the impact of SustainSahel's interventions in the sites of Niakhar and Koulikoro. The dissemination strategy and its implementation were key to this research effort by WP3 and the WP8 and WP3 teams were very often in contact regarding the planning and progress of the activities.

Interactions with the Innovation Platforms (WP2)

Interactions with IPs, which were coordinated by WP2, provided a great platform for the in depth discussion of what the lead farmers (many of them members of the IPs themselves) have learned and seen during the open field days. This proved very instrumental in the identification of problems as well as solutions to overcome those problems related with the CSL practices targeted during the open field days. The main conclusions of those discussions are well described in deliverable 2.3.

5.2 Expanding the project's outreach

5.2.1 Collaboration with the DAAPS project

The activities of SustainSahel's spin-off project DAAPS (Disseminating appropriate agroforestry practices) significantly enhanced SustainSahel's outreach and impact, increasing the number of farmers learning about appropriate agroforestry practices, but also distributing thousands of tree seedlings to farmers, building wells and implementing tree nurseries. The project lasted for two years and ended in December 2023. Table 4 shows a compilation of the main results.

Table 4. Overview of results and achievements of SustainSahel’s spin-off project DAAPS, between 2022 and 2023

Country	Number of OFD*	Participants in the OFD*	Trained nursery caretakers	Trees planted	Participants in video screenings	Awareness raising events	New wells
Senegal	4	841	30	12,164	-	-	10
Mali	4	665	120	25,311	1,093	-	-
Burkina Faso	4	568	134	41,986	600	925	-
Total	12	2,074	284	79,461	1,693	925	10

*Open Field Days

Besides the organization of a total of 12 open field days, the DAAPS project also implements tree nurseries in several villages in the above-mentioned areas, which produce local tree and bush seedlings to be distributed to farmers. Additionally, the three NGOs organize video screenings in villages with videos that have been co-selected with SustainSahel’s team.

5.2.2 Collaboration with other H2020 and EU-DESIRA projects

Collaboration with DESIRA’s FairSahel project: The SustainSahel project is in close contact with the FairSahel project, with which concrete bridges have already been forged. The two projects collaborated closely in two of the project’s sites, with an exchange of information between the projects’ teams and synergies in the organization of the innovation platforms of Sikasso and Koussanar.

Co-development of a policymakers-focused video for the 5th AU-EU Agriculture Ministerial Conference, June 2023: SustainSahel participated in the development of the content for a policymakers-focused video, together with SustIn Africa, EVABELT, Soils4Africa and UPSCALE projects, in an effort led by the latter. The video compiled results and recommendations from the five projects, and was shown to the participants of the 5th African Union – European Union Agricultural Ministerial Conference in June 2023 during the thematic session “Research and Innovation for smarter policies and technologies”, chaired by Martin Heydon (Minister of State at the Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine, Ireland). The video is [available online](#).

Organization of an InfoPoint session in Brussels, Belgium, September 2023: SustainSahel led the organization of an InfoPoint on September 5th, with the participation of the FairSahel project, titled “Improving farmers’ livelihoods in the Sahel through agroforestry and the agroecological intensification of farming systems”. The InfoPoint is a mechanism established by DG INTPA (European Commission) and provides a relevant platform to share key results and recommendations to an audience close to the European institutions, but also to the general public. The InfoPoint session took place on the 5th of September and counted with 218 participants, the majority of which online.

Side event at TropenTag, Vienna, Sep 2024, jointly organised by EU-Funded projects under SFS-35-2019-2020: Five EU-funded projects focused on sustainable intensification in Africa (Soils4Africa, SustInAfrica, EWA-BELT, UPSCALE, and SustainSahel) joined forces to present and discuss their key findings and communication efforts during the TropenTag 2024 conference at the The University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences in Vienna. The event provided a brief introduction to the projects, presented some of

D8.8: Open Field Day (M60)

the key results, and engaged the audience in a critical discussion. More details on SustainSAHEL's newsletter. The preparation and organisation of the event occurred during the reporting period.

Panel session at the Tropical Summit, Lisbon, Nov 2024, jointly organised by EU-Funded projects under SFS-35-2019-2020: The same five EU-funded projects focused on sustainable intensification in Africa (Soils4Africa, SustInAfrica, EWA-BELT, UPSCALE, and SustainSahel) organized a panel discussion to present and discuss their key findings and communication efforts in a panel session at the Tropical Summit in Lisbon, November 2024.

H2020 EU-Projects under SFS-35-2019-2020 Policy Event in Brussels, May 2025: The conference demonstrated the power of collaborative research, bringing together projects funded by Horizon 2020, the DeSIRA initiative, and the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation. SustainSahel's participation alongside projects like EWA-BELT, FairSahel, HealthyFoodAfrica, and others showcased the coordinated effort to advance sustainable agriculture across Africa. This collaborative spirit reflected SustainSahel's own partnership approach, uniting 17 partners from 9 countries across Europe and Africa under FiBL's coordination. A video on this conference is [available online](#).

4. Appendix – Images of SustainSahel’s open field days

Figures 3 and 4. Poster presentations in a village setting during an open field day of phase 2 in Niakhar, Senegal.

D8.8: Open Field Day (M60)

Figures 5 and 6. Lead farmers in Koulikoro, Mali, receive printed posters with SustainSahel's research results presented in a visual way in a dissemination event on the 28th of May, 2024.

Figures 7 and 8. One decentralized dissemination event of phase two in the site of Koulikoro, Mali. The event took place on the 15th of November at the field of lead farmer Mamoutou Diarra in the village of Mafeya, and focused on the dissemination of the use of bush biomass as mulch and fodder (*Gliricidia sepium* in the picture).

D8.8: Open Field Day (M60)

Figures 9 and 10. One decentralized event from phase two in the site of Saria, Burkina Faso, October 2024.

Figure 11. One farmer in Burkina Faso shows the indigenous *Piliostigma* bush, which they learned how to use as mulch and for compost making.